

Author: Chaire BEA

Contributing authors: Amandine Rave, Marianne Berthelot

Graphics: Salomé Bled

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18921780

<https://chaire-bea.vetagro-sup.fr/en/>

July 2025

Species sheet – All about goats!

A good climber and curious creature, goats also have many cognitive abilities. This new educational sheet, following on from the one on rabbits, is an opportunity to revisit the characteristics and needs of goats!

This species sheet has been reviewed by Marianne Berthelot, research project manager for ruminant welfare at ANSES.

Sensory abilities

Sight

Panoramic field of view (320-340°).

Can easily detect movement behind it without moving its head.

Sees colors but cannot distinguish **red** from **green**.

DID YOU KNOW?
Goats have **rectangular** pupils. When they tilt their head, their pupils rotate to remain horizontal (which allows them to see approaching dangers, even while grazing).

Thanks to its large pupils, the goat has good night vision.

Smell

Its highly developed sense of smell plays a major role in its reproductive behavior.

The '**buck effect**' consists of introducing a buck into a herd in order to induce estrus in females. The buck's odor plays a key role in stimulating their hormonal activity.

Taste

Goats have a good sense of taste and can recognize **salty, sweet, sour, and bitter** flavors.

They are highly selective in their diet (*grasses, herbs, buds, and shrub leaves*) but maintain a varied diet.

DID YOU KNOW?
Goats have **self-medicating** abilities.

Hearing

Goats are sensitive to **high-pitched** and **low-pitched** sounds.

They can **identify their offspring** by their vocalizations.

Goats have difficulty locating the spatial origin of a sound.

Touch

Sensitivity to touch

Most sensitive areas

*Thermal sensitivity**

***The thermal comfort of goats depends on the breed, and temperature perception depends on humidity and air speed.**

DID YOU KNOW?
Touch plays an important role in social bonding, particularly between mother and child.

The goat's lips are very sensitive and enable it to sort through food.

It likes and needs to scratch! (*grooming behavior, stress reduction*).

